

Veterinærinstituttet
Norwegian Veterinary Institute

Why this workshop?

The Covid-19 pandemic reminds us that there will always be new and emerging infectious diseases that pose a serious threat to human and/or animal health. Such infectious diseases can have a reservoir in wildlife or domestic animals, or be zoonoses. This kind of threat can happen in every country, requesting actions in the different sectors and collaboration between sectors. The question is; are you prepared to deal with it in a One Health fashion?

In this workshop, we will inquire how signalling and response to zoonoses is organised in Norway and who plays a role in it. We will use “systems thinking” to, hopefully, open the perspective on opportunities to enhance the collaboration between sectors. We will look closer at stakeholder analysis and system mapping, two tools that are useful for disease management in general.

What is systems thinking?

Systems thinking is a way of looking at and talking about reality that helps us understand and work with complex systems that interact with their environment. It helps conceptualizing many elements that interact and behave, and that are in their totality at times beyond our capacity to grasp. Systems thinking allows us to analyse details without losing the sense for the whole. It offers a set of tools for capturing, analysing and communicating about systems.

Watch a 2-minute introduction by the systems thinking pioneer Peter Senge at MIT:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eXdzKBWDraM>

Watch a 5-minute video about systems thinking in public health:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GPW0j2Bo_eY

What will we do?

During this workshop, we will employ a systems approach to reach a better understanding of the interactions between the Norwegian actors of zoonoses.

The primary aims are:

- To identify the actors involved in the signalling and response to zoonoses in Norway
- To identify various other stakeholders, their roles, motives, and perspectives
- To gain an inventory of existing links and relationships
- Possibly, include biological and/or social mechanisms related to zoonoses.

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The session will result in a visual representation, or “map”, of the way the field of zoonoses signalling and response is organised in Norway today.

With the map, we will:

- Identify critical control points for the evaluation of the signalling and control of zoonoses
- Identify missing communication links
- Identify missing data and knowledge
- Gain a better understanding of the dynamics between different elements, sectors and disciplines, such as reinforcing and balancing feedback loops
- Gain a holistic view on biological and social dynamics involved in zoonoses.

Why should you attend?

To learn about the systems approach as a way to tackle wicked problems:

- It helps addressing problems with no perfect solution(s)
- It helps crowd sourcing and co-creating knowledge, and facilitates cross-cutting ideas
- It helps anticipating impacts in a more holistic way and facilitates negotiating trade-offs
- It can be applied to other complex challenges in your daily tasks
- To present your perspective and that of your institution
- To be part of a seminal process collecting our current knowledge about zoonoses governance in Norway, building the system map as a common point of reference
- To generate new ideas for interventions, policy development and stakeholder engagement
- To initiate an iterative process to improve zoonoses governance progressively
- To lead the conversation about zoonoses in Norway

When and where?

Thursday 14 January 2021.

From 9 am to 5 pm.

The workshop will be in Oslo. The venue is to be confirmed.

For questions, please contact:

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Extended explanation: why this workshop?

The emergence of zoonoses, and infections with an animal reservoir, pose a serious threat to both human and animal health. Zoonotic pathogens can originate from livestock, pets, wildlife but they can also be vector borne or dangerous because they are resistant against certain antimicrobials. It is clear that working towards a world with less zoonotic disease burden requires collaboration at all levels and between the veterinary, human, food and environmental sector. In Europe a lot is already arranged in legislations, regulations and for many (especially foodborne) zoonoses surveillance systems are in place, providing early warning and timely response and control. Also new and emerging zoonoses and infectious diseases, which are not monitored, can become public and/or animal health threats. Every country can face such threats unexpectedly. Examples are BSE/CvJD in the UK and Q-fever outbreak in The Netherlands, or the most recent Covid-19 outbreak in Wuhan.

As a result of the above mentioned outbreaks, the UK as well as The Netherlands have implemented a risk analysis structure covering signalling, risk assessment, risk management and risk communication in a One Health approach. These One Health approaches are stimulated also by the [Global Health Security Agenda](#). One of the goals of the Global Health Security Agenda at the national level is to introduce an operational framework that supports multi-sectoral notification for outbreaks of suspected zoonotic origin in the early stage of emergence (prior to efficient human-to-human transmission). The framework should address outbreaks that occur in both animals and humans at a similar time and/or place. However, there is no blueprint for such One Health risk analysis structures (OHRAS) due to different organisation of food production systems, organisation of ministries, geographic factors, and differences in cultures between countries.

In the One Health EJP project [COHESIVE](#), implementation guidelines are drafted to support countries to organise risk analysis activities at the national level. For countries who like to do this, it is important to determine the exact goal of the OHRAS and the context in which the OHRAS will be

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organised. In order to get insight in the context, meaning the current system you operate in, a systems mapping approach can be very helpful and a systems mapping tool will be part of the guidelines.

A workshop facilitated by Simon Rüegg

Dr. Rüegg is a veterinary epidemiologist and experienced systems thinker at the University of Zürich, Switzerland. He has within the EU COST Action “Network for Evaluation of One Health” edited the [Integrated approaches to health: a handbook for the evaluation of One Health](#). Further, he has published many peer-reviewed articles on the subject, and has been solicited for presentations and workshops by the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the American Veterinary Medical Association, the US Defence Threat Reduction Agency and the French CIRAD, among others. For more details, please consult Dr Rüegg’s [researcher ID profile](#).

A workshop in the framework of the COHESIVE project from the One Health EJP consortium

The workshop is part of the project [COHESIVE](#), which is part of the [One Health EJP consortium](#) in which more than 38 European partners are involved. COHESIVE is led by Dr. Kitty Maassen from the Dutch National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). One of the aims of the project is to support member states in Europe in creating One Health approaches to strengthen the collaboration between food, medical, and veterinary professionals with respect to early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses.

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